

Resolutions from the VFSMOD Workshop, Piacenza, Italy, September 2024¹

Synthesis

VFSMOD (Muñoz-Carpena, 2021; Muñoz-Carpena et al., 1999, 2010) is a mechanistic model that simulates vegetated filter strips (vegetation buffer zones) of given characteristics and quantifies their effectiveness in reducing sediment and pesticide loads, including plant protection products, transported by surface runoff from adjacent treated fields. In regulatory practice, VFSMOD supports higher-tier environmental risk assessments (ERA) by evaluating VFS as a mitigation measure for pesticide runoff into surface waters.

Initial guidance for VFSMOD parameterization in EU FOCUS Step 4 scenarios was provided by Brown et al. (2012) and integrated that year into the Surface Water Assessment eNabler (SWAN) tool. SWAN is a user-friendly interface to assist in assessing application of exposure mitigation processes based on FOCUS Surface Water Step 3 SWASH-PRZM-TOXSWA calculations ([SWAN - ESDAC - European Commission](#)).

VFSMOD was evaluated and recommended for use in SETAC MAgPIE (Alix et al., 2017), with recommendations to replace its semi-empirical pesticide trapping algorithm. Subsequent updates addressed these concerns by incorporating: a) a mechanistic trapping equation (Reichenberger et al., 2019); b) dynamic sediment property calculations (Reichenberger et al., 2023); c) consideration of shallow water tables (Muñoz-Carpena et al., 2018; Fox et al., 2018; Lauvernet & Muñoz-Carpena, 2018); d) partial remobilization of pesticide residues in subsequent runoff events (Muñoz-Carpena et al., 2015, 2018a; Ritter et al., 2023); and e) assessment of VFSMOD use long-term FOCUS scenarios (Reichenberger et al., 2022).

Despite these improvements, VFSMOD remains rarely used in EU regulatory assessments and is not yet accepted in zonal evaluations. [The Southern Member State Steering Committee \(SMS-SC, 2021\)](#) agreed that VFSMOD may be used by applicants in their draft registration reports to calculate PEC_{sw} at the state level when proposing risk mitigation measures at the zonal level for the authorization of plant protection products. However, the use of FOCUS Landscape & Mitigation (L&M) Guidance remains mandatory. When the zonal rapporteur member state includes risk mitigation measures calculated using both FOCUS L&M and VFSMOD, the acceptance of these proposed measures for product authorization is at the discretion of each member state. The committee also emphasized the need for risk regulators and assessors to advance the implementation of such models at the zonal level to promote harmonization of risk mitigation measures—an area that currently lacks consistency. At the national level, FOCUS Step 4 simulations with SWAN-VFSMOD are explicitly accepted only by Poland (per national guidance; Polish Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, 2025), Bulgaria (Southern Zone Member States, 2023), and Malta (Pitarokili, 2023), and are occasionally used to support dossiers in Hungary, Italy, and Portugal.

Limited adoption stems from uncertainty regarding its performance across all soil textures in FOCUS scenarios, as noted on the JRC website ([SWAN - ESDAC - European Commission](#)): *“As the uncertainty whether the mitigation being modelled with VFSMOD is achieved for all the other soil textures that the FOCUS scenarios cover still has to be independently evaluated, VFSMOD has only rarely been accepted for use in EU level assessments and decision making. VFSMOD estimated runoff reductions may be accepted by some national competent authorities, in assessments supporting national product authorisations. Applicants are advised to confirm the situation with each competent authority.”*

¹ Steering Committee members:

- *Academia*: Rafael Muñoz-Carpena, Roger Holten, Nicoleta Suciuc
- *Industry*: Robin Sur, Stefan Reichenberger, Horatio Meyer, Peter Rainbird, Bernhard Jene, Amy Ritter, Andrew Bailey
- *Regulators*: Elena Alonso Prados, Igor Kondzielski

To address these concerns, a VFSMOD Workshop was organized as a hybrid meeting on the 3rd of September 2024 associated with the XVII Symposium on Pesticide Chemistry in Piacenza, Italy (<https://symposiumpesticide.org/>), with ~70 attendants from regulatory bodies, academia and industry. At the workshop, and in the technical report thereafter (Reichenberger et al, 2025), the JRC website comment above was addressed by demonstrating VFSMOD's effectiveness across most soil texture groups in FOCUS scenarios, with only minor exceptions affecting small fraction of the EU FOCUS area ($\leq 3.6\%$). These results support VFSMOD's suitability for regulatory use.

The workshop was conceived as a stepping-stone to aid in the successful implementation of VFSMOD into the EU regulatory framework. Its aim was to bridge the state-of-knowledge about VFS modelling and the regulatory state-of-practice. It aimed to identify the answer to the question: "*What considerations and actions are needed for adoption and harmonization of VFS quantitative mitigation in the regulatory context?*". The workshop consisted of three parts:

- a) The first part provided background for further discussions by means of eight presentations ([see agenda](#)) prepared by the members of the steering committee on: i) introduction to the VFS mitigation problem and objectives; ii) a survey of current acceptance of VFSMOD in EU submissions; iii) VFSMOD in regulatory practice: a Polish perspective; iv) overview of North American VFSMOD use; v) advances on the latest VFSMOD version for regulatory use; vi) derivation of updated SWAN-VFSMOD scenarios for FOCUS Step 4 simulations; vii) SWAN-VFSMOD implementation; and viii) use in other ERA tools. All presentations are available at [Summaries « SPCXVII : Symposium on Pesticide Chemistry](#) (password: Symposium@2024). The workshop presentations and discussion videos are also available directly from the Workshop organizers (please contact nicoleta.suciu@unicatt.it).
- b) The second part of the workshop was a plenum for discussion by the audience on the practical aspects of successful implementation and use of VFSMOD as a regulatory model. It focused on the following problems/questions developed and proposed by the steering committee:
 - *Do you see an advantage in a mechanistic, quantitative approach to estimate runoff mitigation over an empirical approach (e.g. empirically derived fixed reduction factors) as currently used in the EU procedure?*
 - *What are the remaining obstacles for the use and acceptability of VFSMOD in regulatory assessments?*
 - *What is needed to accept VFSMOD in regulatory assessments?*
 - Additional discussion point: The acceptance of VFSMOD could enable further mechanistic approaches that are required to assess run-off from spot applications or for site-specific run-off assessments in spatially explicit modelling.
- c) The third part focused on elaborating the synthesis and resolutions of the workshop by the participants. All the opinions expressed during this discussion and additional questions asked were recorded in the form of minutes, which were used to prepare the proposal for this document. The proposal was presented to the audience and discussed during this third part. The results of that discussion were once again recorded in the form of minutes, which were used to prepare the first version of this document with the resolutions and future action points (Table 1).

Additional discussion was facilitated through an off-line 3-month review (Dec. 2, 2024-February 31, 2025) of this document. Workshop participants (contacted through the Symposium attendant list), the Central regulatory working groups, and Steering Committee/environmental fate experts of Central and Southern Member States were invited to submit comments. We received comments from public agencies at 8 Member States (AT, DE, ES, HR, IR, IT, NO, PL) and private sector (Corteva and Rifcon). Comments received and

revisions (Table 2) made to accommodate those comments were shared again with the respondents in summer 2025.

This Resolutions Document is the result of the synthesis and review after this process and will also be published on the Symposium website and Zenodo for public reference (Munoz-Carpena et al., 2025).

Resolutions

During the final Synthesis session, the attendees expressed support for the following resolutions and action items (Table 1). For transparency, specific comments received from respondents during the document review process and details of how they are addressed in the final document are included in Table 2.

Table 1: Workshop resolutions and action items

	Resolutions	Action Items
1.	VFSMOD's mechanistic approach for incorporating VFS mitigation in regulatory environmental exposure assessments is superior to a simplistic, fixed efficiency factors approach.	<p>a) Clarify and explain the concept of the upstream catchment used in SWAN and in conjunction with VFSMOD. The scenario assumption for the upstream catchment with VFSMOD should be the same as with the reduction factors according to FOCUS L & M.</p> <p><u>Follow-up:</u> The same scenario assumptions of SWAN apply to both classical SWAN (FOCUS LM reduction efficiencies) and SWAN-VFSMOD, and they are identical to the assumptions formulated in FOCUS LM report (Ter Horst et al., 2009). Ter Horst et al. (2009) also analyzed the aspect of dilution by the untreated area of the upstream catchment. This was further expanded upon by Reichenberger et al. (2014). See references below. Ter Horst MMS, Adriaanse PI, Boesten JJTI (2009). Mitigation of runoff in the FOCUS Surface Water Scenarios. Note of the fate group of the Environmental Risk Assessment team of Alterra on the interpretation of the mitigation of runoff in the FOCUS Landscape and Mitigation Report (2007). AlterraRapport 1794, ISSN 1566-7197. 35 p. Reichenberger S, Bach M et al. (2014). Impact of step 4 scenario assumptions and VFSMOD parameterisation on the effectiveness of vegetative filter strips in reducing PEC in surface water. 7th European Modelling Workshop, 21-23 October 2014, Vienna, Austria; oral presentation</p> <p><u>Caretaker:</u> steering committee¹</p>
2.	VFSMOD input parameters related to the FOCUS scenarios must be well documented and published in a peer reviewed journal and technical report	<p>a) Prepare a peer-reviewed paper describing the new VFS scenarios for the four FOCUS R scenarios (as presented in the workshop).</p> <p>b) Within the paper, describe the protectiveness of the four new VFS scenarios for the different soil texture classes (as presented in the workshop).</p> <p>c) Include a comparison to the fixed reduction factors as provided in the FOCUS Landscape & Mitigation report.</p> <p>d) In addition, a technical report for earlier access and covering the same aspects as the paper and model inputs will be prepared to be published on the JRC (where SWAN is available for download) and Zenodo websites.</p> <p>e) Details of VFS scenarios and parameterization are also being added to the technical document for SWAN 5.2.</p> <p><u>Follow-up:</u> The peer-reviewed paper will be ready for submission by 01/2026. The report has been completed on 03/2025, forwarded on 07/2025 to EFSA and the EU Commission, and published on 10/2025 (Reichenberger et al., 2025).</p>

	Resolutions	Action Items
		<u>Caretaker:</u> steering committee members ¹ and collaborators
3.	<p>A remaining issue discussed in the workshop is the comment on the recent EC Compendium (March 21, 2024, Table pg. 29 Field Management Measures, “Tbd”) and on JRC website about the representativity and validation of the VFS scenarios in VFSMOD. The paper and report (Resolution 2 above) is considered as a prerequisite for regulatory acceptance of VFSMOD.</p>	<p>a) Following publication, the Compendium was updated on May 23, 2024 so that the comment related to (Table p 29, comment “Tbd” and “Is it possible to use the item to refine the risk assessment?”) is no longer related to the use of VFSMOD for quantitative mitigation but it now pertains to harmonization of field data (“Are harmonized exposure data available to be used in a risk assessment?”). The new column title only makes sense in the context of the use of field measured data (reduction percentage) to quantify mitigation rather than modelling tools like VFSMOD.</p> <p>b) Since wider public interest in the tool is increasing as a result of publication of the EC Compendium, a dissemination technical report should be prepared presenting in a simplified way the concept of VFSMOD, its implementation into SWAN and via this into tiered FOCUS SW assessment scheme as a part of Step 4 evaluation, and an analysis of the current and anticipated implementation into the regulatory scheme as a fully viable tool.</p> <p>c) Validation by EFSA and implementation into the EFSA FOCUS version control would further support the full regulatory acceptance of the VFSMOD tool.</p> <p><u>Follow-up:</u> The initial question on the use of VFSMOD is now addressed in the ensuing Report prepared (Reichenberger et al, 2025), where the results of the VFS FOCUS scenarios for the different EU soil texture classes are shown to be more protective than the alternative empirical L&M coefficients.</p> <p><u>Caretaker:</u> European Commission, JRC, zonal risk managers with support from academics and stakeholders as requested. The dissemination report will be prepared by the workshop organizers and will be submitted at the end of 2025.</p>

	Resolutions	Action Items
4.	As SWAN allows application of VFS mitigation with both VFSMOD and Landscape & Mitigation efficiencies, harmonization of the use of the tool must be developed.	<p>a) In consultation with risk managers, a guidance needs to be developed to harmonize the use of the tool and define the appropriate one to apply. VFSMOD mechanistic approach allows for specific scenarios conditions and produces a more realistic and transparent evaluation of the expected efficiency of the VFS in that context. As a result, there would be situations where VFSMOD offers less or more conservative results than the empirical reduction factors. Consistency guidance on the use of both alternatives should be developed (no “cherry picking!”).</p> <p><u>Follow-up:</u> A guidance will be developed in the first quarter of 2026.</p> <p><u>Caretaker:</u> risk managers groups with support from academics and stakeholders as requested</p>
5.	The adoption of VFSMOD in the regulatory context should continue immediately without waiting for FOCUS SW repair tools.	<p>a) As there is still no fixed release date for the FOCUS Surface Water Repair software tools and they will likely introduce their own issues, do not wait. The use of VFSMOD is independent from the version of FOCUS SW and directly applicable to the new FOCUS SW repair. VFS scenarios were also developed in the new report with FOCUS SW repair assumptions (Reichenberger et al., 2025), so they are also compatible with the future release of the FOCUS SW repair when available.</p> <p><u>Follow-up:</u> A new version of FOCUS SWAN for FOCUS SW repair is also under development that incorporates VFSMOD with compatible parametrization and will be ready when the repair action is approved.</p> <p><u>Caretaker:</u> Capgemini Engineering, with support from stakeholders as requested</p>

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- *Academia:* Rafael Muñoz-Carpena, Roger Holten, Nicoleta Suci
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Table 2. Responses collected from stakeholders, responses and action items.

#	Country	Organiz.	Pag/ line	Comment	Response	Action/ Conclusion
1	Austria	AGES 24/07/2025	AGES General Position	<p>Given the current regulatory landscape, VFSMOD cannot be used in core zonal assessments or as a substitute for FOCUS Step 4 mitigation measures. Its outputs are not accepted for deriving regulatory endpoints in the Central Zone or by most Member States. Where its use is considered for national authorisation purposes, prior agreement with the competent authority is essential.</p> <p>Until further harmonisation, peer-reviewed implementation guidance, and soil-specific validation are achieved, VFSMOD remains an exploratory or supplementary tool. Its use in EU regulatory submissions should be limited to supportive analysis unless explicitly requested or accepted by national authorities. Applicants should adhere to currently endorsed approaches under the FOCUS framework for risk mitigation in surface water exposure assessments.</p>	<p>Yes, the synthesis text has been revised to reflect this comment. It is correct that currently most MS do not accept VFSMOD but some accept it on a case-by-case basis, and for the case of Poland SWAN-VFSMOD is accepted and regularly used. Regarding the last part of the comment, please also note that not all member states adhere to currently endorsed approaches under the FOCUS framework as stated. For example, Germany does not accept FOCUS (2001).</p> <p>As suggested, soil-specific validation has been addressed in the new technical report on the VFS parametrization of the FOCUS scenarios, and the peer-reviewed paper that will be submitted in January 2026. The report can also serve as implementation guidance.</p>	<p>Technical Report: https://zenodo.org/records/1740044 4</p> <p>Peer-reviewed paper: ongoing</p>
2	Austria	AGES 24/07/2025	AGES General Position	<p>At present, VFSMOD is not part of the officially accepted toolbox for surface water exposure assessments under the FOCUS framework. It is not referenced in EFSA guidance or any harmonised interzonal working documents. The European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC) notes that uncertainty regarding the model's</p>	<p>The JCR concern on the validity across soil textures is now addressed as described above and presented to EFSA. Please note that JRC does not mention uncertainty about the performance of VFSMOD, but uncertainty about the protectiveness of the SWAN-VFSMOD results.</p>	

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				performance across the full range of 22 FOCUS soil textures has prevented broad acceptance. Consequently, VFSMOD has only been accepted in a limited number of national submissions, and even then, under specific conditions.		
3	Austria	AGES 24/07/2025	AGES General Position	<p>Although recent workshops and publications have demonstrated improvements in the model's algorithms and validation status, certain limitations persist:</p> <p>1) Evaluations show that VFSMOD underperforms for specific soil texture classes (e.g. very fine soils in R1, medium-fine soils in R2), which may lead to insufficient mitigation estimates in vulnerable areas.</p> <p>2) Use of VFSMOD requires detailed site-specific data and expert knowledge that are not typically required for other Step 4 mitigation options. This undermines consistency and reproducibility.</p> <p>3) The model's reliance on event-based calculations complicates harmonisation with the standardised exposure scenarios of the FOCUS framework, which are built on deterministic, conservative principles.</p> <p>4) There is no harmonised EU guidance or procedural document describing how VFSMOD should be applied in regulatory assessments, how its outputs are to be interpreted, or how comparability between dossiers can be ensured.</p>	<p>On 1): This statement is inaccurate. VFSMOD underperforming for specific soil textures would mean that it does not predict VFS efficiency accurately for specific soil textures. In fact, many peer-reviewed papers on VFSMOD evaluation against measured data support its prediction accuracy (e.g. visit https://abe.ufl.edu/faculty/carpena/vfsmo/citations.shtml).</p> <p>Comparison with measured data was not part of this study, but to provide an update of SWAN-VFSMOD scenarios. We suppose that what AGES really mean is that the pesticide reduction ΔP calculated with the new SWAN-VFSMOD scenarios are not protective for all soil textures. We need to point out two things here:</p> <p>i) It is perfectly normal and even by definition that a 90th percentile worst case in space does not cover the remaining 10 % of the area of interest. The CDFs we produced essentially to reflect soil vulnerability.</p>	

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					<p>Hence, if we select a 90th percentile worst case soil profile, 10 % of the area will have more vulnerable soil profiles.</p> <p>ii) Some soil texture classes have higher vulnerability than others. If we wanted to achieve an at least 90th percentile worst case for each texture class, we would end up with an extreme overall worst case: For instance, for R1, where the most vulnerable texture class is VF (very fine): for R1 / class VF the 10th percentile ΔP is 15.154 % (Reichenberger et al., section 3.5; table B-variant_R1_KOC100_DUR8_CORINE_full.xlsx in digital annex). For the whole CDF for R1 (all texture classes together) this ΔP value corresponds to a cumulative area percentage of 0.56 %. We would thus have an overall 99.44th percentile worst case.</p> <p>On 2): We strongly disagree. The SWAN user does not need more site-specific data or more expert knowledge for running VFSMOD than for running FOCUS PRZM or TOXSWA. All scenario parameters except VL (VFS length in flow direction) are pre-defined. Hence, the SWAN user only needs to</p>	

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					<p>choose VL. In conclusion, the use of SWAN-VFSMOD is very much harmonized with the use of the other models in FOCUSsw.</p> <p>On 3) We also disagree on this point. VFSMOD calculates all processes that determine the VFS trapping efficiency during the event, but also provides calculations between events that are leveraged by SWAN in a continuous simulation framework. All calculations with VFSMOD (event-based and between events) are mechanistic and deterministic, and thus in line with the other models used at FOCUS step 4 (PRZM and TOXSWA). This is not the case for the currently used fixed factors approach (which is essentially event-based, empirical, and based on very limited data). Moreover, VFSMOD peer-reviewed testing has demonstrated that the predictions are much more accurate than applying fixed reduction efficiencies. For instance, for large runoff events VFSMOD yields more conservative results than the fixed efficiency approach and</p>	

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					<p>thus helps avoid underestimating risk.</p> <p>On 4) We agree. This comment is closely aligned with the resolutions adopted by the Workshop participants. In the next steps agencies like AGES should participate to identify the format and type of guidance needed. Some options might be an EFSA guidance, an EFSA SO, a document by the EC (e.g. a more comprehensive chapter in the “Compendium”). Participation of the national EU authorities would help to scope such a deliverable. The examples of Poland and other MS that at times have accepted VFSMOD show that also MS level decisions can be taken, but it would be very desirable to harmonize approaches at the zonal and EU level.</p>	
4	Austria	AGES 24/07/2025	Line 29 onwards	The text states that VFSMOD has 'seldomly' been used in regulatory assessments and that only 'a few' Member States have accepted it. It would be helpful to specify which Member States currently accept VFSMOD and under what conditions. This would support transparency and help applicants understand the landscape. Consider	Good point. We have added this in the last version of the text. At the national level FOCUS step4 simulations with SWAN-VFSMOD are only explicitly accepted by Poland per national guidance (Polish Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, 2025), Bulgaria (Southern Zone Member States,	

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				including a tabulated summary or an appendix	2023) and Malta (Pitarokili, 2023), and occasionally supporting dossiers in Hungary, Italy, Portugal and Spain at the moment	
5	Austria	AGES 24/07/2025	Line 32 onwards	While the workshop addresses JRC's concern about coverage of all soil textures, it remains unclear whether a formal independent evaluation has been conducted or is planned. We recommend that the text clearly describe the nature and extent of this validation, including who performed it, how it was peer-reviewed, and what regulatory bodies were involved.	This will be addressed in part by the peer-reviewed publication in preparation (submission in January 2026). AGES and other interested agencies could also form a review committee of new technical reports, possibly under Zonal, EFSA or EC oversight. The organizers would greatly appreciate AGES engagement on this.	
6	Austria	AGES 24/07/2025	Line 42 onwards	The text presents analysis suggesting that VFSMOD results are protective for most soil texture classes, except for two exceptions. It would strengthen the argument if the document included absolute ΔP values or ranges for transparency, or a reference to a supplementary data table.	Detailed statistics for ΔP and PECsw from the comparison of the new SWAN-VFSMOD scenarios with the fixed efficiency approach are included in the Supplementary Information of the manuscript, and also in the digital annex of the report (Reichenberger et al., 2025). For instance, detailed results for each VFSMOD simulation can be found in tabular format in R1234_30mm_noWT_out_2024 0610.xlsx (option classical Green-Ampt).	
7	Austria	AGES 24/07/2025	Line 96-97	The document would benefit from a clearer separation between scientific advancement and regulatory	We agree and we added brief information on this in paragraph 4 of the final document. Some	

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				endorsement. Consider adding a dedicated section explicitly outlining the current regulatory status of VFSMOD at EU and national levels, including any pilot applications or case studies.	<p>specific details are also provided below:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. EFSA Conclusion: So far, only for Mecoprop-P (EFSA, 2017), VFSMOD was presented and evaluated in the final EFSA Conclusions. 2. Zonal Level: Southern Member States Steering Committee (SMS SC): “...in their meeting on 12 May 2021 agreed that the use of this tool for the calculation of PEC_{sw} at SMS level and for the proposal of RMM at zonal level can be used by applicants in their proposal of DRR for the application of authorization of plant protection products...” 3. National Level: Poland (regularly accepted), Occasionally: Hungary, Bulgaria, Italy, Portugal, Spain 	
8	Austria	AGES 24/07/2025	Table 1 Point 2	We strongly support the preparation of a peer-reviewed paper and technical report. However, given the importance of harmonisation, we propose that these publications should be jointly reviewed by a panel including representatives from	Regarding the technical report (Reichenberger et al., 2025): It has already been sent to EFSA and also been published on Zenodo and will be distributed among workshop participants with these resolutions.	

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				EFSA, JRC, and zonal regulatory bodies prior to finalisation, to ensure broad scientific and regulatory acceptance.	Similar to comment #5 above, external review would be indeed welcome. We would be happy to edit the manuscript (Reichenberger et al., in preparation) based on the feedback on the published technical report.	
9	Austria	AGES 24/07/2025	Table 1 Point 3	The document describes updates to clarify the status of VFSMOD in the Compendium, yet ambiguity remains regarding its acceptability at EU level. We recommend explicitly stating whether EFSA considers VFSMOD an acceptable model for PECsw refinement at Step 4, or what steps remain for such acceptance.	This statement must be made by EFSA, possibly as a conclusion of the resolutions and documents derived from this effort. We have sent the report and these resolutions for their perusal, and will also send them future products. We encourage AGES and all other agencies to engaging with EFSA to this end.	
10	Austria	AGES 24/07/2025	Table 1 Point 4	The risk of selective model choice is acknowledged but not operationalised. Consider proposing explicit decision criteria or a decision tree for when to use VFSMOD vs. empirical mitigation. This would provide clear guidance to applicants and authorities.	As agreed by workshop participants, from a scientific point of view the empirical fixed efficiency approach should be made obsolete based on its limited data support and lack of extrapolability from individual studies. This is in fact the strength of a mechanistic approach based on first principles, its extrapolability once it has been extensively tested as VFSMOD has. We cannot think of any situation where the fixed efficiency approach would be scientifically preferable.	

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					The implementation in SWAN-VFSMOD with the documentation provided in the technical report and other derived documents represent the operationalization, and the tool can be readily used.	
11	Austria	AGES 24/07/2025	Table 1 Point 5	We agree that VFSMOD is conceptually independent of FOCUS SW repair, but the text should clarify how compatibility with the forthcoming FOCUS SW version will be ensured, particularly in terms of input parameter harmonisation and model interoperability.	Agreed. This has now been expanded on in Resolution 5 (Table 1). The VFSMOD input parameters will not change. SWAN-VFSMOD will just run with a longer .p2t file (20 years) as input instead of a 12 month .p2t file --> larger number of events. Consequently, there are hardly any adjustments needed to make SWAN-VFSMOD compatible with FOCUSsw repair. The SWAN developers are already finalizing a "repair-ready" version.	
12	Austria	AGES	Table 1 action 3	Inclusion of this point at the third resolution: e) Validation by EFSA and implementation into the EFSA FOCUS version control would be needed for full regulatory acceptance of the VFSMOD tool.	Thank you for your comment. We agree to the principle and have expanded this point on the final document. While this does not stop its use by individual member states, to standardize its use, we strongly support getting VFSMOD/SWAN under FOCUS version control and engaging with EFSA on the process to achieve this. A step on this direction is the new Scenario Report and ensuing	New point included in action point 3 of Table 1: e) Validation by EFSA and implementation into the EFSA FOCUS version control for full regulatory acceptance of the VFSMOD tool.

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					publication that addresses EFSA standing comments. In addition, the use of VFSMOD within SWAN provides standardization of its use in FOCUS scenarios by Member States	
13	Croatia	HR-Department for PPP and biocides Centre for Plant Protection, Zagreb	Table 1 action point 4a	<p>We would like to express support for the VFSMOD workshop resolutions. According to the publication of the Compendium of conditions of use to reduce exposure and risk from plant protection products, two ways are proposed in risk assessment:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Field evidence-based approach using the fixed factors from the FOCUS Landscape and Mitigation report on a lower-tier;</i> 2. <i>Dynamic modelling of the VFS performance under the environmental conditions of the regulatory run-off scenarios with VFSMOD (SWAN).</i> <p>As SWAN is developed to apply VFS mitigation with both VFSMOD and Landscape & Mitigation efficiencies, we agree that there is need to harmonize the use of the tool and define the appropriate one to apply in the regulatory context. Please note that VFSMOD has not yet been used in regulatory risk assessment at HR national level.</p>	<p>Feb. 4, 2025</p> <p>Thank you for your comments and participation in the workshop and resolutions.</p>	<p>HR supports action point 4 a in table 1</p> <p>No action needed</p> <p>Closed</p>
14	Germany	UBA	Table 1, resolution 1 a	<p>Comment Table 1, resolution 1 a): Action should be specified or clarified in our opinion:</p>	<p>Yes, the text on this resolution has been revised to address this comment. Here are additional</p>	<p>This FOCUS SW assumption is beyond the scope</p>

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				<p>Especially the fraction equipped with buffer stripes (fb) of 20 % of the upper catchment as defined in SWAN should be discussed and evaluated (by MMSS and EFSA) as mentioned by Ter Horst et al. (2009) and Reichenberger et al. (2014). Please note that the upstream catchment definition was not part of the FOCUS L+M and was defined by SWAN developers. Hence, the definition of the upstream catchment is questionable for both, VFSMOD and reduction factors.</p>	<p>details for your perusal. There are two different “20 %” assumptions.</p> <p>1. FOCUS surface water (FOCUS, 2001) assumes that 20 % of the upstream catchment area of the stream are treated. (This yields a dilution of the edge-of-field runoff concentration of 1:5 in most cases).</p> <p>2. SWAN assumes that precisely these 20 % of the upstream catchment are equipped with VFS. Consequently, in FOCUS step 4 simulations, the reduced runoff fluxes (water and pesticide flux) of the 20 ha upstream are combined with the unchanged runoff water fluxes of the remaining 80 ha upstream catchment. SWAN bases this assumption on the FOCUS LM report (FOCUS, 2007), which is very vague in formulation. The vagueness of the recommendations in FOCUS LM is extensively discussed in Ter Horst et al. (2009).</p> <p>The clearest statement in FOCUS LM is on page 144-145 of the FOCUS LM report (vol 2): “The assumption could be further refined on the basis of</p>	<p>of the VFSMOD workshop focus, but pertains to the general use of mitigation practices.</p> <p>Closed.</p>

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					<p>landscape analysis and/or evidence of agronomic practice, probably involving the use of a catchment-scale model. In such cases 1) all areas assumed to be treated with the pesticide under consideration should be subjected to the reduction in runoff volumes, and 2) the assessment will need to consider the extent to which runoff intercepted by the buffer is purged of pesticide residues prior to any movement to surface water".</p> <p>In the end, Ter Horst et al. (2009) conclude: "We concluded that the way the SWAN software handles reduction in runoff is in line with the assumption of the FOCUS WG on landscape and mitigation that the buffer zones are installed at the 21 ha with treated crops only, and not on the remaining 80 ha of the upstream catchment."</p>	
15	Germany	UBA	Table 1 resolution 2	<p>We would like to point out that the VFSMOD model input parameter FWIDTH is a very sensitive input parameter regarding the effect of concentrated flow. Therefore, this parameter should be validated, harmonized and well documented.</p>	<p>This comment likely stems from the UBA GERDA project, where some flow concentration values are proposed. While flow concentration is not typically considered in regulatory applications, the suggested values could be used as reference for those interested.</p>	<p>Note that while the use of FOCUS_{sw} at EU level is already accepted, for those MS interested in incorporating flow concentration VFSMOD offers</p>

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						the opportunity to implement this readily in their domains. Closed.
16	Germany	UBA	Table 1 resolution 2, point d):	In our opinion, a peer-review and validation of VFSMOD, the new VFS scenarios and parametrization within SWAN 5.2. by Member States and EFSA is required (see resolution 3 below).	Please refer to comment #3-1) and #12 from AGES Austria.	See comment #3-1) and #12 from AGES Austria.
17	Germany	UBA	Table 1, resolution 3, point b):	At first the required peer-review and validation of VFSMOD, the new VFS scenarios and parameterisation within SWAN 5.2. by Member States and EFSA needs to be completed in our opinion.	Please refer to comment #3-1) and #124 from AGES Austria.	See comment #3-1) and #12 from AGES Austria.
18	Germany	UBA	Table 1, resolution 3, point d):	Parameterisation of SWAN and VFSMOD is crucial.	Please refer to responses to comment #12 from AGES Austria.	See comment #12 from AGES Austria.
19	Germany	UBA	Table 1, resolution:	VFSMOD in the context of FOCUS repair was outside the direct scope of the workshop and was only discussed as a side aspect. Thus, it should not be presented as an independent resolution point. In general, the adoption of VFSMOD is independent of the availability of the FOCUS surface water repair tool. Rather, addressing the resolution points 1-4 as well as a validation and harmonisation process between the regulators of the member states and	Agreed, we believe this refers to Resolution 5b.	We revised the document to separate “repair” into a new point in resolutions. Closed.

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				the EFSA is crucial for the implementation of VFSMOD.		
20	Germany	CORTEVA Agriscience, Env. Exposure Assessment	Table 1 action point 5	The collated feedback of Corteva colleagues is that we agree with the content of the resolution document which makes sense to us. We support that implementation of VFSMOD (in either FOCUS version) and implementation of FOCUS REPAIR should be regarded as independent processes.	Thank you for your comments and participation in the workshop and resolutions. Noted	Support of action point 5 in Table 1. No action needed at this step Closed
21	Germany	RIFCON GmbH	General comment	Please excuse that I did not answer! If I remember correctly, the synthesis and resolutions you sent describe very well what was discussed in the workshop. So, I don't have any comments to add. Many thanks for compiling this!	Thank you for your comments and participation in the workshop and resolutions.	No action needed Closed
22	Germany	UBA	paragraph 2	Comment: However, the parameterisation of SWAN has not been validated or peer reviewed by MMSS or EFSA yet.	SWAN is designed as an automator of FOCUS step 4 "manual calculations" (https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/projects/swan). Thus, intrinsically it follows the same prescribed parametrization and practices for FOCUS step 4.	The paragraph 2 is reworded to clarify that SWAN is not a model but a user-friendly interface to use FOCUS step 3 results for FOCUS step 4 calculations. Closed
23	Germany	UBA	paragraph 3	Comment paragraph 3: Question: By whom? It would be helpful to add this information.	Agreed	Text revised to add citations. Reference list included at the

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						end of the document Closed
24	Germany	UBA	Comment part 3 WS c):	Unfortunately, there was only limited time to discuss the proposal of the synthesis and resolutions during the workshop	Agreed, discussion is essential. Because of this, 2 rounds of consultations on the document followed, as summarized in this Table 2.	Text revised to indicate that extended opportunity was given by providing comments to this Resolutions document. Closed
25	Ireland	Pesticide Registration Division, Department Agriculture, Food and the Marine	General comment	Thank you for sharing the resources from this workshop. We found them to be very informative. We appreciate all the efforts of all those responsible for the ongoing development of the tool and the scenarios. A lot of work has been done. We do not have anything to add to the current version of the document as we find that the resolutions also capture our views at this stage.	Feb. 4, 2025 Thank you for your comments and participation in the workshop and resolutions.	No action needed Closed
26	Italy	ICPS- International Centre for Pesticides and Health Risk Prevention, Lombardy Region.	to Table 1, 4a) "...a guidance needs to be developed to harmonize the use of the tool and define the appropriate one to apply".	Once the new VFSMOD version will be released and implemented in SWAN, it will be crucial to develop an EU guidance document recommending the adoption of VFSMOD in regulatory context and harmonizing the use of the tool. Since it is generally agreed that VFSMOD mechanistic approach is superior to the empirical reduction	Feb. 4, 2025 Thank you for your comments and participation in the workshop and resolutions. The new report and research publication on VFS scenarios addresses parametrization to harmonize VFSMOD use with SWAN, and the new version of SWAN has been released now with such standard	IT ICPS supports action point 4 a in table 1 IT ICPS proposes that the VFSMOD approach replaces the empirical one to be further discussed among

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				<p>factors approach, it should be clarified under which circumstances the use of FOCUS LM reduction efficiencies may still be the preferred option at Step 4.</p> <p>Considering the above, we believe that it would be appropriate that the new VFSMOD approach will replace the empirical one, in order to avoid situations where VFSMOD is used only as a refinement option for more critical active substances.</p>	<p>parametrization for R1-R4 scenarios. We agree that the guidance document mentioned in the Table will help address harmonized use of the VFSMOD option in SWAN is a good idea. As this was already included in the Table no changes were made on the revised text, but the comment is reflected here in the Responses Table. Please see also comment #5 from AGES and responses.</p> <p>Noted</p>	<p>MS once action point 4a in Table 1 is conducted</p>
27	Poland	IOS- Institute Environment al Protection		<p>-SWAN-VFSMOD allows for more flexibility with respect to buffer strip width (VL) than SWAN with fixed efficiencies from FOCUS LM. While the latter allows only for 10 and 20 m buffer strip width, with SWAN-VFSMOD one can simulate any buffer strip width and can thus achieve better harmonization with no-spray buffers (e.g. both buffers equal to 5 m). (not original wording, it has been summarized by RMC, SR and RS)</p> <p>-VFSMOD provides a refinement step. This is not “cherry-picking”, but an allowable practice, used in Poland (for instance). From our practice with all four R scenarios, either at EU or zonal/MS level, we never saw a situation in which, for the same width of the vegetated</p>	<p>Thank you for your comment and support for these resolutions.</p> <p>The new SWAN-VFSMOD version (integrated in SWAN 5.3) is more conservative than the previous one from SWAN 5.01. We will see a significant number of situations where VFSMOD predicts less pesticide retention than FOCUS L&M reduction factors, allowing for the identification of unsustainable uses.</p>	<p>No action needed</p> <p>Closed</p>

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				buffer zone VFSMOD returned PEC values for runoff higher than those obtained using FOCUS L&M reduction factors. Whenever I had problems with high runoff, running VFSMOD helped me significantly in overcoming it.		
28	Poland	IOS- Institute Environment al Protection		From our point of view, the focus should be on making VFSMOD efficient with SWASH and SWAN, also not disregarding the upcoming release of FOCUSsw repair.	Agreed. A new version of SWAN will be released shortly this year that incorporates high execution efficiency leveraging multiprocessing capabilities of modern PCs. A new version for FOCUS repair is also being developed to be ready when the repair is approved.	Pending on the SWAN developers. No further action needed from this group. Closed
29	Poland	IOS- Institute Environment al Protection		Another request as a practitioner (i.e. person, which uses SWAN and VFSMOD rather routinely for getting the information on the exposure assessment). I would like readily available graphical presentation of the results obtained within SWAN, using either FOCUS L&M reduction factors or VFSMOD to mitigate runoff. This would be a great asset. At present, with TOXSWA re-run after mitigation, the results are given for 100 days after the maximum peak concentration occurs and the fate/ecotox experts may be not aware whether over the longer time span there is a pulse exposure or not, what may significantly change the results of the assessment. I realise there are tools for doing this,	Although this request for a new SWAN feature is not within the scope of these resolutions, it has been noted by the SWAN developers and added to the list of desired new features for the next release pending funding.	Pass on the SWAN developers. No further action needed from this group. Closed

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				but switching from one tool to another, is time consuming.		
30	Poland	IOS- Institute Environment al Protection		Finally, the success of this project is really important not only for us in our agency, but also for DG SANTE and European Commission, because at present many evaluated actives do not pass the re-evaluation, or with severe restrictions, because of SW exposure/risk assessment, realistic quantitative mitigation with current tools like SWAN is a pressing need	Thank you for conveying this need. This was also the consensus of many of the symposium participants.	These resolutions are hopefully a step towards this objective. Closed
31	Spain	INIA-CSIC	General comment	We welcome the work related to the analysis of VFSMOD with other soil textures of FOCUS scenarios. We also consider the process of the validation and endorsement by the COM and MMSS start asap once the reports are published.	Thank you for your comments and participation in the workshop and resolutions.	Agreed on the pressing need to endorse the application at different levels. We have added this explicitly to Resolution 5 for further action. Closed

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